

Method of Surgical Treatment of Bladder Exstrophy

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Abstract

Surgical correction of bladder exstrophy is reconstructive in nature and should be performed in specialized pediatric surgical centers. The most pathogenetically justified approach is bladder reconstruction using local tissues; however, this technique requires specific conditions. When reconstruction with local tissues is not feasible or when long-term outcomes are unsatisfactory, the proposed surgical method represents the procedure of choice. An analysis of treatment outcomes in 22 children treated using the developed method was conducted. The proposed method is an effective alternative in the surgical treatment of bladder exstrophy.

Keywords: bladder exstrophy; artificial bladder; surgical correction; separate defecation and urination.

Introduction

Despite more than a century of clinical experience, the problem of treating bladder exstrophy (BE) remains relevant today. This is due to the complexity of the malformation, its variability, and the persistently high rate of unsatisfactory treatment outcomes. Questions regarding the optimal timing and selection of surgical techniques for both newborns and older children remain unresolved.

Currently, two principal approaches to the surgical treatment of bladder exstrophy are recognized. The first involves bladder reconstruction using local tissues. The second is directed toward urinary diversion into the intestinal tract and includes procedures without separation of urine and feces, as well as partial or complete urinary diversion.

Bladder reconstruction using local tissues is considered the most pathogenetically justified approach. However, this procedure requires an adequately sized bladder plate and must be performed in the early days of life, before secondary changes in the bladder wall develop. Mandatory correction of pubic bone diastasis is also required. Due to the complexity of the procedure, adequate birth weight and the absence of severe associated anomalies are necessary. When these conditions are not met, intestinal urinary diversion procedures are indicated.

Materials and Methods

A novel method for the surgical treatment of bladder exstrophy was developed and implemented in our clinic (Patent No. 30906, dated March 11, 2008).

The operation is performed as follows. A lower midline laparotomy is carried out with excision of the bladder plate and transection of the ureters at their orifices. The sigmoid colon is mobilized, taking into account the length required for perineal descent. The sigmoid colon is transected, and the proximal end is closed. The ureters are implanted into the rectal lumen using an invagination technique, after which the rectum is closed with a two-layer suture.

At the level of the peritoneal reflection, the seromuscular layer of the rectum is incised along the anterior semicircumference. Demucosalization of the rectum is performed distally along almost the entire semicircumference, leaving an undissected strip no wider than 1 cm at the 5–6 o'clock position. **Figure 1. The sigmoid colon was transected, the ureters were implanted into its lumen, the reservoir was sealed, and distal demucosalization of the rectum was carried out.**

From the perineal side, the separated mucosa is excised in a cone-shaped manner directed downward, and the edges are sutured using a continuous suture.

Figure 2. Excess separated rectal mucosa was excised, a neourethra was constructed, and mobilization and descent of the colon were initiated.

The neourethral canal along the anal canal should not exceed 1 cm in width. The sigmoid colon is pulled down intrarectally, and cutaneous–mucosal sutures are applied circumferentially around the anus and the newly formed urethra. **Figure 3. The sigmoid colon was mobilized and brought down to the perineum intrarectally.**

From the abdominal cavity, the edges of the incised muscular layer of the rectum are sutured to the descended colon, and the pelvic floor is peritonealized. During the operation, the newly created reservoir is treated with a 1–2% povidone–iodine solution.

As a result, the newly formed urethra and the descended colon are positioned within the rectal sphincter complex, ensuring continence of urine and feces and preventing their mixing.

Figure 4. The margins of the descended colon were anastomosed to the cutaneous–mucosal junction circumferentially around the anal opening and the neourethra.

Figure 5. The descended colon and the constructed neourethra are positioned within the sphincter complex of the rectum.

Results

Between 2002 and 2014, 22 children with bladder exstrophy were treated in our clinic. Fourteen children aged 8 months to 3 years underwent primary surgery using the developed method. Eight patients required repeat reconstructive surgery due to unsatisfactory outcomes of previous treatment; in five cases, bladder reconstruction using local tissues had been performed during the neonatal period.

Three children had previously undergone surgery in other institutions between the ages of 3 and 9 years. Two had undergone the A. V. Melnikov procedure, and one had undergone the Michelson–Ternovsky procedure.

Treatment outcomes were evaluated one year after surgery. Long-term follow-up data were available for 12 children over a period of up to seven years. Assessment included urinary and fecal continence, the presence or absence of urine–feces mixing, the condition of the ureters and kidneys according to ultrasound and excretory urography, and laboratory blood and urine test results.

In eight patients, outcomes were assessed as good. These children maintained urinary and fecal continence during both daytime and nighttime. Defecation occurred no more than three times per day. Urination occurred during defecation and separately up to 5–6 times per day, with three children reporting distinct urges for urination. Rectal examination revealed adequate sphincter tone and an empty rectal ampulla. Speculum examination showed the neourethral opening at the 6 o'clock position, freely accommodating a catheter. Ultrasound and excretory urography revealed no abnormalities in renal structure or function.

In four patients, results were considered satisfactory. These children maintained continence; however, two experienced periodic nocturnal urinary leakage, and one four-year-old child had more frequent leakage. No distinct urges for urination or defecation were noted. One child developed a stone in the constructed bladder 2.5 years after surgery, requiring surgical removal. Another child was diagnosed with unilateral vesicoureteral reflux and subsequently underwent anti-reflux surgery.

Discussion

When bladder reconstruction using local tissues is not feasible or yields unsatisfactory long-term results, the developed method may be considered the procedure of choice. The technique provides reliable urinary and fecal continence and prevents their mixing, addressing key functional challenges associated with bladder exstrophy.

Conclusion

The proposed surgical technique represents an effective alternative for the treatment of bladder exstrophy, particularly in patients for whom standard bladder reconstruction using local tissues is not possible or unsuccessful.

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